

Functioning of District Central Cooperative Banks in Chhattisgarh

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Abstract: The functioning of the cooperative credit system in India is characterized by two distinct arrangements. There are two categories of credit structures: short-term and long-term. This paper focuses solely on evaluating the functioning of the short-term credit system. Primary Agricultural lending Societies form the bedrock of the short-term lending system, with linkages to both District Central Co-operative Banks and the State Co-operative Bank. To reflect its status as a federal organization, the DCCB welcomes participation from all PACS and other associated functional societies, while SCB participation is limited to affiliated DCCBs. The functioning of District Central Cooperative Banks of Chhattisgarh for the period of 2015-16 to 2019-20 is being evaluated in the current study. It is worth noting that there are 351 DCCBs operating in India as per RBI's 2021 report. The functioning of DCCBs in Chhattisgarh State is being evaluated using secondary data for the study.

Keywords: Co-operative bank, Credit Structure, Financial System, Banking Regulation Act 1949.

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1. Introduction

Financial institutions serve as the backbone of any advanced economy. It's crucial to the health of any economy and one of the financial system's main pillars. The banking sector is one of the oldest financial intermediaries in the financial system. The banking system is the fuel injection system which spurs economic efficiency by mobilising, saving and allocating them to high-return investments. Research confirms that countries with a well-developed banking system grow faster than those with a weaker one. The banking system reflects the economic health of the country. The strength of any country's economy hinges on the financial system's stability and efficiency, which in turn depends on a sound and solvent banking system.

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Section 5(A) of the Banking Regulation Act defines banking in India as "any entity which transacts banking business" and Section 5(B) defines the objective of banking business as "accepting deposits of money from the public for lending or investing." As a result, a bank is a business that deals with credit and money. It takes public deposits, disburses money to individuals in need, and aids in the transfer of monies from one location to another. According to the International Co-operative Alliance Statement of Co-operative Identity, a co-operative is an independent group of people who come together voluntarily to meet their shared economic, social, and cultural needs and goals through a business that they all own and run democratically. Cooperatives are based on the ideas of self-help, self-responsibility, democracy, equality, fairness, and solidarity. Cooperative members uphold the moral principles of transparency, honesty, social responsibility, and compassion in the manner of their founders.

It is a framework that allows management to supervise and oversee organisations in the best interests of stakeholders and other parties, promoting more openness and better, more timely financial reporting. It is a way of conducting business in accordance with particular moral standards. Corporate governance cannot be defined in a way that is agreed upon by everyone. It can be broadly construed as a system of organising, managing, and controlling a business with the aim of achieving long-term strategic goals to satisfy shareholders, staff members, customers, and suppliers as well as to adhere to legal and regulatory requirements, in addition to addressing environmental and local community needs. Its primary focus is on responsible corporate leadership, which is an important component of corporate democracy. A system of checks and balances between the Board of Directors, Management, Auditors, and shareholders' savings is what corporate governance aims to create.

2. Literature review

Bhaskaran and Josh (2000) found that cooperative banking institutions' low recovery performance contributes to NPA rise even after prudential rules. They advised legal and regulatory changes to make cooperative credit institutions more efficient, productive, and lucrative. Singh and Singh (2006) researched money management in Punjab's DCCBs, focusing on financial margin. A rising amount of own funds and recovery worries raised the margin of Central Co-operative Banks, resulting in a larger provision for non-performing assets. Campbell (2007) focused on the link between non-performing loans (NPLs) and bank collapse and urged for appropriate bank bankruptcy regulation for emerging and transitional economies suffering from NPLs.

Thirupathi (2012) studied the expansion of DCBs in India using selected measures such as deposits, credits, and credit-deposit ratios. The expansion of DCBs and their branches exhibited a negative tendency up to a specific period, then a small positive trend, although

cooperative membership has increased. During the research period, capital, reserves, and borrowing nearly doubled with little change. During the research period, the number of employees increased, raising management costs per worker. He advised DCCBs to enhance technology and create customer-friendly practices to compete with commercial banks.

Kumar (2014) compared public, private, and international banks. All commercial banks were NPA-checked six years ago. If recovery prospects are low, public-sector banks must lend to disadvantaged communities. It analyses the demise of public sector banks but does not demonstrate how they overcome lending to poorer sectors and NPAs. Banerjee et al. (2018) analyse Gross NPAs and Net NPAs in private and public sector banks from 2009-2016 to evaluate if they affect asset quality. Private sector banks have lower Gross Non-Performing Assets and Net Non-Performing Assets; hence they perform better.

Reddy and Chandraiah (2019) investigate Indian cooperative banking. This research focused on cooperative banks in India's branch networking, capital, advances, deposits, borrowing, and exceptional performance. They examined Co-operative Banks in India. During the research period, cooperative banks performed well, raising earnings and utilising management skills effectively. Membership growth increased deposits. This paper is designed to investigate the role of the district central cooperative bank in Chhattisgarh and to study the progress of the district central cooperative bank in Chhattisgarh. For a collection of secondary data on the progress of the district central cooperative bank, five years i.e., from 2015-16 to 2019-20 were taken as the reference period.

3. Methodology

The present study is based on the secondary data published by the National Federation of State Cooperative Bank Ltd. (NAFSCOB). The required data for the study purpose were collected from a number of reference books, journals, and official sites.

3.1. District Central Co-Operative Banks

The following definitions of district central co-operative banks are provided by the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development: "Central co-operative bank means the principal co-operative society in a district in a state, the primary purpose of which is to finance other co-operative societies in the district. In certain regions of India, a District Central Co-operative Bank (DCCB) is a cooperative bank that operates at the district level. According to The Banking Regulation Act of 1949, all District Central Co-Operating Banks are registered and governed by the Reserve Bank of India. The DCCBs are situated in a central town or the district's administrative centre. It was founded to offer banking to

the agriculture industry's rural hinterland, with most of its branches located in these rural and semi-urban areas.

3.2. Function and Roles of a DCCBs

The District Central Co-Operative Banks play a vital role. Some of these are as follows:

Banking institutions: In accordance with the Banking Regulations Act, the Reserve Bank of India has acknowledged the DCCBs as legitimate banking entities. They will take deposits from the general public and will lend money to individuals as well as organizations like fundamental cooperative societies. They are subject to the plethora of regulations that the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) would on occasion promulgate. The Banking Regulations Act of 1949 includes particular restrictions in light of the unique nature of their ownership, development role, etc.

Face of the cooperative movement: Giving financial support to the Primary Co-operative Societies it is linked within the district and is one of the District Central Co-operative Banks' most significant responsibilities. These organisations fall under a wide range of categories, such as principal urban cooperative banks, producers' cooperative societies, salary earners' cooperative societies, consumers' cooperative societies, and primary agricultural credit societies. The District Central Co-operative Banks' support and growth of the Primary Agricultural Credit Societies, however, is one of their most crucial responsibilities. The PACS attached to them is periodically inspected by DCCB officials. The DCCB is the primary source of funding for the PACS, and the DCCBs' supervisors frequently check on the PACS' lending programme. The DCCB's line of credit allowing PACS members access to production loans for crops is one of the most significant. Many PACS also carry out a variety of tasks, including selling fertiliser and other agricultural supplies, and many of them distribute ration items as part of the Public Distribution System (PDS). As a general rule, the PACS do not own a major resource base of their own; hence, the DCCBs are the ones who provide the funds for such operations and any other loans that are distributed to members. The deposits made by the members are a significant source of the PACS's own resources. A specified number of deposits of this kind that are collected by PACS are placed as reserve deposits with the DCCBs to protect the interests of the depositors who are PACS members. In addition to this, the DCCBs are helpful to PACS in terms of capacity-building. They provide training programs for members of the PACS board who serve as directors and secretaries. Additionally, periodic seminars are held to inform the PACS staff and members of significant events that may affect them.

Leader in agriculture lending: In the past, DCCBs have played a crucial role in meeting the agricultural sector's immediate needs for credit. Production loans as well as marketing loans made available to members are included here. The "Scale of Finance," a standard formula used to loan amounts for each of the district's primary agricultural commodities, is typically used to determine which farmers receive production loans. The financial scale is determined by adding up the price of all inputs, including labour, used to produce the crop. The credit needed per hectare for cultivation is calculated alongside the yield and market value of the product. The DCCB organises a group of experts called the "District Level Technical Committee" to determine budgetary allocations. Representatives from the agricultural department, banks, NABARD, etc. are all represented on the District Level Technical Committee.

Financial assistance: District central cooperative banks provide financial assistance to their customer. Financial assistance is any type of monetary help or aid that a person, organisation or government receive. so, banks need to function properly. The primary cooperative and rural development banks must be encouraged to become more productive and work efficiently. The financial assistance may be in the form of guarantees, loans, subsidies, or welfare payments. tax allowances and grants are some examples of financial assistance.

The objectives performed by District Central Co-operative Banks are as follows:

- 1) To finance the primary societies for agricultural purposes.
- 2) To develop and extend banking facilities in rural areas and make people more aware of banking and its overall developments.
- 3) To make a secure location available for the main societies' financial reserves to be invested.
- 4) To simplify the farmers' access to finance and financial resources.
- 5) To undertake non-credit activities.

3.3. Progress of district central cooperative banks in Chhattisgarh

Table 1 represents the progress of district central cooperative banks in Chhattisgarh state over five years. They indicate that total membership increased from 103461 in 2015-16 to 104028 in 2019-20 which shows a growth of DCCBs in Chhattisgarh. Paid-up capital, reserve and deposit rates are increasing adversely on the other side of the borrowing rate and loans and advances show a declining rate. Working capital increased by 7.99% in the years 2019-20. Every Total number of employees increased in a year which indicates the positive progress of the district central cooperative bank in Chhattisgarh state.

Table 1: Show the progress of District Central Cooperative Banks in Chhattisgarh (Amount in lakhs)

Particulars	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
No. of District Central Co-operative Banks	6	6	6	6	6
No. of offices, including head offices	264	266	268	284	291
Total Membership	103461	103588	103895	103986	104028
Paid up capital	31421	35166	40244	43773	46776
Total Reserves	91343	109268	122816	139347	142435
Total Deposits	511127	593795	652699	1157530	1114602
Total Borrowings	102702	92825	116221	84932	75426
Working Capital	810550	896894	1002175	1396779	1508466
Investments	448800	495299	542660	944929	1005013
Total loans issued	425375	423980	556026	462389	447664
Total Loans Outstanding	252668	263711	328980	375603	281531
Total Demand	399994	947799	524408	613521	674245
Total collection	288165	328712	384673	441017	519373
Balance collection	111829	119087	139735	172504	154872
Total Number of Employees	2153	2203	2238	2429	2390

Sources: Report of NAFSCOB year from 2015-16 to 2019-20.

3.4. Services that district central cooperative banks provide

- Deposits
- Savings Bank Account
- Current Account
- Recurring Deposit
- Fixed Deposit
- Cash Certificate
- Loans
- Loans to Salaried Employees
- Home Need Loans
- Loans to Pensioners
- Loans under Women Entrepreneur Development Scheme
- Building Mortgage Loan
- Education Loan
- Housing Loan
- Loan to Physically Challenged Persons

The Services offered by the Cooperative banks include-

- Clearing
- Safe Deposit Locker
- Automated Teller Machine (ATM)
- Demand Draft / Pay Order

4. Findings and Suggestions

The largest obstacle to the progress of cooperative banks operating effectively has been political interference in their operations. The issue of growing past due in cooperatives is one that the decision-makers are quite concerned about. The growing backlog slows down economic growth by negatively affecting cooperatives' ability to lend money, provide timely and enough credit to agriculture, and interrupt the flow of credit to farmers over time. Up until now, cooperative banks have had to rely heavily on the government, RBI, and NABARD to help them get new loans. They cannot become self-sufficient with the money they have on deposit.

4.1. Suggestions

- The banks ought to make the transition to more modern banking practices such as banking online, using credit cards, and so on.
- It is imperative that banking institutions work toward enhancing their client service to a greater extent.
- The DCC Bank is required to keep appropriate liquid resources and, margins, conduct a proper examination of loans, and make an effort to improve the quality of its workforce.

5. Conclusion

It appears that cooperative banks are essential to the development of rural communities. They also have to deal with a variety of issues. In other words, the Khusro Committee's recommended that cooperative banks function as a whole system and increase their independence. The higher banking authority should support the smaller banking authorities in the manner of mother institutions. They ought to exercise power, direction, leadership, supervision, and control. There should be reciprocal support, assistance, accountability, and responsibility to ensure positive and productive interaction between the system's tiers. The reserves and deposit mobilisation profit ought to be distributed equally. The primary driver of cooperative deposit mobilisation progress is self-reliance. The intended approach for deposit mobilisation, which is the key to success for cooperative banks, is to mobilise little amounts from as many individuals as possible. To survive in the modern day, contemporary practises should work in tandem with some institutions.

Computerization and poor leadership ought to be stopped. They should develop themselves using cooperative ideas.

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